

Effect of Work Environment and Giving Incentives to Employee Employee Spirit (Case Study at PT. Benua Penta Global in Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant)

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ABSTRACT

One of the reasons why employees continue to work at PT. The Global Penta Continent at Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant is a work environment. Where is if the work environment is good, comfortable, provided by Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant, employees can work well and optimally as well as increase work spirit in carrying out the duties and responsibilities of each employee. And vice versa what if the work environment provided by Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant is not good and there is no sense of comfort, then employees cannot work properly and optimally and there is no work morale in.

This research uses quantitative research methods that contain numbers. The population in this study was all employees at the Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant. Sampling with a sampling technique with a sample of 50 employees. Data collection techniques using a questionnaire with a Likert scale that has 5 alternative answers. And analyzed using multiple linear regression and the coefficient of determination, R² with SPSS software for windows version 16.

The results of the study show the following, (1) The work environment has a significant effect on employee morale in Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant, (2) The provision of incentives has a significant effect on employee morale in Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant, (3) There is a positive and significant effect between the work environment and the provision of incentives to employee morale at Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.761 and a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.579. This means that 57.9% of the employee morale in the Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant area.

KEYWORDS: *Work Environment (X1) Giving Incentives (X2) and Work Spirit (Y)*

1. Rear Background

Issues An agency in any form, both large and small scale is inseparable from the elements of human resources. It must be realized that the role of humans as workers is very important, both individually and in groups. Humans are the main driving force for the smooth process of achieving organizational goals. This is because however sophisticated the equipment used by an organization will still be meaningless without the humans who operate it. The position and role of human resources is very important for an institution in achieving its goals. The management of human.

Providing incentives can increase or decrease employee morale. Because if employees view their incentives and work environment as inadequate, their morale can decrease dramatically. This results in not achieving the company's mission to get high profits. The purpose of providing incentives is to increase employee morale in the effort to ignite company goals. Providing incentives will also have an impact on employee productivity and retain high-performing employees to remain in the company.

The incentive is one means to improve employee morale, by way of knowing what needed them and trying to fulfill

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them. According to Mangkunegara (2017) states the understanding of incentives is as follows: Incentives are a form of money given by the leadership of the organization to employees so that they work with high motivation and achievement in achieving organizational goals as recognition of work performance and employee contributions to the organization.

Another method that is no less important than providing incentives is the work environment. We can see the facts for ourselves where a good, safe, and comfortable work environment makes employees who work at a company will be enthusiastic at work. According to Kaswan (2017) stated that the work environment must be arranged in order to create a healthy, safe, clean, comfortable, and pleasant atmosphere that can reduce physical and mental stress and increase productivity and quality of work life.

Based on some understanding of the work environment and the provision of incentives above, it can be concluded that how important the work environment and incentives are in influencing employee morale in a company.

PT Benua Penta Global is one of the companies engaged in services, namely restaurants where places to sell food and drinks that prioritize friendly facilities and services as a selling point, even though prices are offered to middle and upper customers. The company started with a legacy recipe that created healthy, nutritious food and drinks that had a legendary taste different from other restaurants. This company stands in the form of restaurant outlets that already have 5 (five) restaurants with different management systems, while 4 (four) restaurant outlets are located in Ma Il Sun Plaza on the 3rd floor and on the 4th floor on Jl. Zainul Arifin No. 7, Madras Hulu, Medan Polonia, Medan City, North Sumatra 20152 and 1 (one) more restaurant outlets are on Jl. S. Parman No.1, Petisah Hulu, District. Medan Baru, Kota Medan, North Sumatra 20151 as for the five restaurants owned by the continent of Penta Global, namely:

1. Xo Suki's restaurant
2. Mantra Manado Restaurant
3. Bank of Seafood (BOS) Restaurant
4. Uncle K Restaurant
5. Chop Tails Cakyo Restaurant

PT Benua Penta Global at Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant has 2 management, namely operational management (the front) and kitchen management (kitchen). The research will be conducted at one of the restaurants owned by PT Benua Penta Global, namely Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant. A good environment will produce better morale as well, and the work environment at PT Benua Penta Global operational section once a week doing briefing where two mutually open about complaints from each employee to one of the managers or supervisors who lead the briefing in overcoming consumer behaviors in order to look for solutions in order to train the mentality of each employee in handling these consumers, and general cleaning is a cleaning activity carried out by the operational section once a month in order to clean the restaurant area of each of each outlet of PT Benua Penta Global. The working environment at PT Benua Penta Global in Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant has a very good operational section where the closeness of the superiors to their employees is very good as you help each other when there are many.

The working environment of the kitchen is also good where employees who work on PT Benua Penta Global kitchen section gets food twice a day in order to reduce the cost of expenses of each employee because this is one of the policies given by the company to kitchen employees. If consumers are in a crowded condition where every Saturday, employees will be multi-functional so that they can help one another, so that customer orders do not arrive complained or canceled due to the time they arrive at the kitchen, the working environment of the kitchen once a week does a briefing where to tell each.

Work environment section the bar every week to do general cleaning to maintain the cleanliness of the kitchen area. If the employee of the kitchen cannot attend because one of the other employees will gather to go and catch the sick employee, because the employee in the kitchen has a very good kinship relationship with each other. The environment good work will provide security and comfort for employees to be able to work in the position of the existing so that the consumer needs can be met. A workforce will be able to

work well if the conditions of work can support the enthusiasm and excitement.

According to Suhadi in Yulianta, quoted by **Putri Raining Sandi (2016)**, revealed that "employee morale can grow if there is a harmonious relationship between superiors and subordinates". With the implementation of good organizational, communication, it is expected that there is a balanced relationship between superiors and subordinates, so that what is communicated can be understood, thought out, and finally carried out with enthusiasm.

To find out the extent of the truth of the work environment and the provision of incentives, really affect employee morale, the authors conducted a study with the title "**The Effect of the Work Environment and Providing Incentives to Employee Spirit on a case study at PT Benua Penta Global**".

2. Problem Formulation

Based on the background stated, the problems formulated in this study are as follows:

1. Is there an influence of the work environment on the work motivation of cloud employees in PT Benua Penta Global?
2. Is there an effect of providing incentives to employee morale at PT Benua Penta Global?
3. Is there an influence of the work environment and providing incentives to employee morale at PT Benua Penta Global?

3. Research Objectives

Based on the formulation of the problem can be identified objectives in this study as follows:

1. To determine the effect of the work environment for work morale, employee at PT Benua Penta Global.
2. To determine the effect of giving incentives to work morale, employee at PT Benua Penta Global.
3. To find out simultaneously the work environment and providing incentives for employee morale at PT Benua Penta Global.

4. Benefits of Research

The benefits of this research are as follows:

1. For employees of PT Benua Penta Global
It is expected that with this research can obtain positive and constructive input, which can be applied by the company in an effort to improve employee morale.
2. For researchers
Adding knowledge and insight for writers on issues relating to the field of managing human resources, especially on issues related to the work environment and providing incentives in connection with the creation of good morale.
3. For academics
It is expected to provide input and as a reference material that will conduct research in the future.

5. Work environment

The understanding of the work environment proposed by **Kaswan (2017)** provides an opinion that the work environment must be arranged in order to create a healthy, safe, clean, comfortable, and pleasant atmosphere that can

reduce physical and mental stress and increase productivity and quality of work life.

performance is above standard performance. This incentive is a tool used to support the principle of fair compensation.

6. Incentives

Giving According to Malaya Hasibuan (2013) in Putri Raining Sandi (2016), the definition of "incentives is additional rewards of services provided to certain employees whose

7. Spirit at work

According to Purwanto (2013) in Sahid Sya Putra (2017) stated that work spirit is something that makes people happy to serve their work where satisfaction, work and pleasant family relationships become part of it.

8. Prior Research

No	Researcher's name	Title	Research methods	Research result
1	Fitriasari (2017)	The influence of the work environment and the provision of assistance in employee work performance in the estuary workshop district of the East Kutai Regency	This study uses Pearson product moment correlation data analysis techniques, and partial correlation analysis, multiple linear regression,	The results of his research that there is a positive and significant effect on the work environment has an influence of 0.524, while the provision of incentives has an influence of 0.570
2	Khomsah Nurul Hidayah (2006) UIN Malang	The influence of the work environment on employee morale in the post daily (Tulungagung Radar)	This research uses quantitative descriptive analysis with multiple linear regression analysis, t test & F test	The results of his research that the work environment has a significant effect on morale, t count is greater than t table.
3	Arifchammad rojai, (2010)	The effect of incentives on the morale of employees of the Sunan Ampel education and social foundation (YPSSA) Sidoarjo.	This study uses a correlation test using the product moment formula	The results of his study found that the correlation test using the product moment formula obtained 0.626 results. And after the results were consulted with the "r" table of product moment 5% with N = 31, so it was found (0.626 > 0.355 > 0.456). From these results, then (H ₀) is rejected and (H ₁)

9. Framework of thinking

Information:

- X₁: Work Environment
- X₂: Providing Incentives
- Y: Work Spirit

10. Hypothesis

Based on the problems that have been raised before, the authors formulate a hypothesis as follows:

- H₁ : There is an influence of the work environment on employee morale at PT. The Global Penta Continent at the Chop Tails Cakyo Restaurant.
- H₂ : There is an effect of providing incentives to employee morale at PT. The Global Penta Continent at the Chop Tails Cakyo Restaurant.
- H₃ : There is the influence of the working environment and the provision of incentives simultaneously on employee morale at PT. The Global Penta Continent at the Chop Tails Cakyo Restaurant.

11. Research Methods

11.1. Research Time and Place

This research was conducted on Rest Oran employees of PT. The Penta Global Continent at the Chop Buntut Cakyo restaurant located in Mall Sun Plaza on floor 4 on JL. Zainul Arifin, North Sumatra 20152. As this study implemented a right starting from the month of July 2019 until the month of August 2019.

11.2. Types of Research

According to Sugiyono (2010), states that explanatory research is a research method that aims to explain the position of the variables studied as well as the causal relationship between one variable with another through hypothesis testing.

11.3. Population and Samples

Understanding the population is **According to Sugiyono (2018)** argues that the population is a generalized area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. According to **Sugioyono (2018)** said that "The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population". To determine the number of samples of the population, the researchers used the sample withdrawal formula proposed by **Suharsimi Arikunto (2017)** to suggest that if the number of respondents is less than 100, then all samples are taken so that the research is population research.

11.4. Types and Sources of

Data Quantitative method is a research method based on positive things that uses certain populations and samples as well as techniques used in sampling usually using random data collection, analyzing data using statistical analysis tools that will answer from a hypothesis according to **Melva Sitanggang and Togu Harlen Lbn Raja (2011)**, as for the two quantitative data sources, namely:

A. Primary data

According to Sugiyono (2010) , defining primary data is as follows: "Primary sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors"

B. Secondary Data

According to Sugiyono (2010), stated secondary data are as follows: "Secondary sources are sources that do not directly provide data to data collectors, for example through other people or through documents".

11.5. Data Collection Techniques

According to Suharsimi Arikunto (1995) quoted by Melva Sitanggang and Tolen Harlen Lumban Raja (2011), stated that the research instrument is a tool chosen and used by researchers in gathering activities so that the activity becomes systematic and facilitated by it. Data collection techniques used in this study in the form of : questionnaire or questionnaire, a list of matches, interviews, observation, and documentation.

12. Results and Discussion

12.1. Validity Test Results

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Work environment1	77.9091	48,691	.726	.970
Work environment2	77.9091	48,691	.726	.970
Work Environment3	77.9091	48,691	.726	.970
Work Environment4	77.8182	47,764	.861	.968
Work Environment5	77.8182	47,764	.861	.968
Work Environment6	77.9091	49,091	.688	.970
Work Environment7	77.8182	47,764	.861	.968
Providing Incentives1	77.9091	49,091	.688	.970
Providing Incentives2	77.9091	49,091	.688	.970
Providing Incentives3	77.9091	49,091	.688	.970
Providing Incentives4	77.9091	49,091	.688	.970
Working Spirit1	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit2	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit3	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit4	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit5	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit6	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968
Working Spirit7	77,6364	48,255	.891	.968

Source: SPSS data management results

Then it can be concluded, based on the table above that all items used in this study have a correlation coefficient value > 0,6 . These results indicate that all items of statements used in this study are valid so that the instrument or questionnaire used in this study is appropriate as a measurement of research.

12.2. Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.970	18

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the table above it can be seen that the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0,970. So it can be concluded that the value of Cronbach's Alpha greater than 0,70 (0,970 > 0,70), the questionnaire in this study revealed reliable.

12.3. Classical Assumption Test Results

12.3.1. Normality Test

A. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
			Unstandardized Residual
N			50
Normal Parameters ^a	The mean		.0000000
	Std. Deviation		1.89804874
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute		.272
	Positive		.272
	Negative		-.221
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z			1,921
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)			.001
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed)	Sig.		.001 ^c
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	.000
		Upper Bound	.002
a. Test distribution is Normal.			

Source: SPSS management results

From the above table explains that the value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic Test is 1,921 and is not significant at 0.001 then H_0 is rejected which means the residual data is not normally distributed. And the results are consistent with previous tests.

B. P-Plot Normal Chart

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Source: SPSS management results In the normal P-plot graph above, it can be seen that the graphic image shows the data spread around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line. Therefore, the data is said to be normally distributed.

12.3.2. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	3,825	3,479		1,099	277		
	Work environment	.638	.117	.609	5,458	.000	.719	1,390
	Incentives Giving	.455	.214	.236	2,120	.039	.719	1,390

a. Dependent Variable: morale

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the calculation of the table above shows the value of tolerance there is no independent variable that has a tolerance value of less than 0.10 which means there is no correlation between the independent variables whose value is more than 95%, where the results of the calculation of the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) also shows things similarly there is not one independent variable that has a VIF value of more than 10. So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

12.3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Scatterplot

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the Scatterplot image above, it shows that the points that are scattered randomly, scattered above and below the zero on the Y axis and do not form a certain pattern that is clear. Therefore, the regression model is said to be said to not experience heterokedasticity.

12.4. Results of Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	3,825	3,479		1,099	.277
	work environment	.638	.117	.609	5,458	.000
	Incentives Giving	.455	.214	.236	2,120	.039

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the results of the spss 16 program output on the *coefficients* describing the regression equation:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 3,825 + 0,638X_1 + 0,455X_2 + e$$

Where:

a: The constant number of *Unstandardized Coefficients* is 3,825.

β_1 : The first regression coefficient number at X_1 (Work Environment) is 0.638.

β_2 : The second regression coefficient in X_2 (Giving incentives) is 0.455.

12.5. Hypothesis Results

12.5.1. Effect of the Work Environment on Work Spirit

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	3,825	3,479		1,099	.277
	work environment	.638	.117	.609	5,458	.000
	Incentives Giving	.455	.214	.236	2,120	.039
a. Dependent Variable: morale						

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the results of SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients in the first regression coefficient of the price variable shows the results of the value to count the working environment is 5.458 and the value of t table with a sign $\alpha = 0.05$ def = nk, IE $50 - 2 = 48$, then the obtained value of t table 1,671, so that it counts $>$ t table ($5.458 > 1.671$). It can be concluded that the working environment positive and significant influence (0,000 0,05) partially to the employee morale at Chop Restaurant Cakyo oxtail, then the work environment H_a received and H_o is rejected

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	3,825	3,479		1,099	.277
	work environment	.638	.117	.609	5,458	.000
	Incentives Giving	.455	.214	.236	2,120	.039
a. Dependent Variable: morale						

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the results of SPSS 16 program output on Coefficients in the first regression coefficient of the price variable shows the results of the value to count the incentive is 3,051 and the value of t table with sign = 0,05, with DF = nk = $50 - 2 = 48$, then the obtained value of t table 1,671, so that t count $>$ t table ($2,120 > 1.671$). It can be concluded that the positive effect of incentives (0,039 0, 05) partially to the employee morale at Chop Restaurant Cakyo oxtail, then the incentive H_a received and H_o rejected.

12.5.2. Effects of the Work Environment and Providing Incentives on the Employee's Spirit

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	301,508	2	150,754	32,355	.000 ^a
	Residual	218,992	47	4,659		
	Total	520,500	49			
a. Predictors: (Constant), giving incentives, work environment						
b. Dependent Variable: morale						

Source: SPSS management results

Based on the table above, it can be seen that F arithmetic is 32,355 with a confidence level of 0,95 ($\alpha = 0.05$), then F arithmetic $>$ F table ($32,355 > 3,15$) and a probability value of 0,000 0,05 so H_o is rejected and H_a receiver. This shows that the independent variables (work environment and incentives) have a significant effect together on work morale.

12.6. Coefficient of Determination

Summary Model ^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.761 ^a	.5779	.561	2.15857
a. Predictors: (Constant), giving incentives, work environment				
b. Dependent Variable: morale				

Source: SPSS management results

1. $R = 0.761$ shows the relationship between the work environment (X_1) and the provision of incentives (X_2) on employee morale (Y) is 76,1 %. This means that the work environment (X_1) and the provision of incentives (X_2) to work spirit (Y) have a close relationship.
2. Figures Square (R^2) of 0.579 shows that the work environment (X_1) and the provision of incentives (X_2) affect the employee morale (Y) of 57.9%, while the remaining 42.1% can be explained influenced by factors other factors not examined in the study.

13. Conclusion

The analysis showed that the work environment and the provision of incentives had a positive and significant effect on employee morale at Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant. Proven by the results of the analysis:

1. X_1 (workplace) shows the kosefisien value by 63,8 %. This means that there is an influence between work environment variables (X_1) on work morale (Y). D ant test t value arithmetic work environment of 5.458, with a value of sigh $\alpha = 0,05$ and $DF = nk$, $IE 50-3 = 47$, then obtained t table one side by 1668 so that it counts $> t$ table ($5.458 > 1.676$).
2. X_2 (incentives) Figures Sguare (R^2) of 0.579 shows that the work environment (X_1) and the provision of incentives (X_2) affect the employee morale (Y) of 57.9%, while the remaining 42.1% can be explained influenced by factors other factors not examined in the study.

14. Suggestion

After conducting research and calculating the data collected, then there are a few points of advice that I want to bring up for Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant. The suggestions are:

1. For Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant, it should pay more attention to employees, workplace conditions, and still maintain good relations and harmony between superiors and subordinates.
2. Providing welfare to employees and so on so that employees provide loyalty to Chop Buntut Cakyo Restaurant and achieving desired expectations with good performance results.

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